

Milestone MS1

OUTLINE OF CAPACITY BUILDING MEASURES FOR EARLY CAREER RESEARCHERS/SCIENTISTS

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MILESTONE 1

Table 1 Document information

Milestone	MS1 Outline of capacity building measures for early career scientists
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Milestone Lead	Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI)
Authors and contributors	Irene Robles Garcia (DMI) Members of the ObsSea4Clim Scientific Steering Committee All partners across the project work packages
Reviewer	Chiara Bearzotti (DMI)

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ABBREVIATIONS

Table 2 List of abbreviations

APECS	Association of Polar Early Career Scientists
CMCC	Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneosui Cambiamenti Climatici
CSIC	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas
DMI	Danish Meteorological Institute
ECOP	Early Career Ocean Professionals
ECR	Early Career Scientists
ECV	Essential Climate Variables
ENS	Ecole Normale Superieure
EOV	Essential Ocean Variables
ESM	Earth System Modelling
ESR	Early Stage Researchers
EuroGOOS	European Global Ocean Observing
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEOMAR	Helmholtz-Zentrum fur Ozeanforschung Kiel
H2020	Horizon 2020
HCMR	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research
M	Month
MOI	Mercator Ocean International
NERSC	Nansen Environmental Research Centre (India) Ltd.
NUIM	National University of Ireland Maynooth
Q&A	Question and Answers
SSC	Scientific Steering Committee
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 About this Milestone

This report provides a first overview of the capacity-building measures offered by the ObsSea4Clim project to early career scientists/early-stage researchers (short ECR/ESR). The goal is to provide opportunities for ESRs to improve their knowledge. The outline presented has been developed by the DMI Project Office (PO) together with the Scientific Steering Committee (SSC). Project partners have contributed with input for each of their respective webinars.

As means of verification for this milestone, this report is shared with the full consortium, and the list of capacity building measures is available in the project website.

1.2 Target audience

The main target audience of ObsSea4Clim's webinar series is early career scientists or researchers (ESR or ECR), who are in the first steps of their careers. A definition adopted by the European Commission and based on the OECD terminology indicates who an ESR or ECR is ¹, but in ObsSea4Clim **we aim to be more open and inclusive**. Primarily ObsSea4Clim addresses ESRs in the early stages of their research careers (despite

¹ A definition adopted by the Commission is the following: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/faq/keywords=/683> A second definition is provided by the OECD [Frascati 2015 manual](#) and applies to the Horizon Europe-funded projects:

Category A – Top grade researcher: the single highest grade/post at which research is normally conducted. Example: 'Full professor' or 'Director of research'.

Category B – Senior researcher: Researchers working in positions not as senior as top position but more senior than newly qualified doctoral graduates (IsCED level 8). Examples: 'associate professor' or 'senior researcher' or 'principal investigator'.

Category C – Recognised researcher: the first grade/post into which a newly qualified doctoral graduate would normally be recruited. Examples: 'assistant professor', 'investigator' or 'post-doctoral fellow'.

Category D – First stage researcher: Either doctoral students at the IsCED level 8 who are engaged as researchers, or researchers working in posts that do not normally require a doctorate degree. Examples: 'PhD students' or Example, not to complete 'junior researchers' (without a PhD).

having a doctoral degree or not). But **everybody is welcome to join these webinars, regardless of their level of seniority and degrees.**

2 Capacity building measures for ESRs

The measures presented in this document have been divided in four different areas: ObsSea4Clim webinars (by project partners, on specific ObsSea4Clim research areas), participation to other existing webinar-series (by ObsSea4Clim ESRs on their research, related to ObsSea4Clim), networking/synergies with existing organisations, and participation to field-work. These sections will be revised and updated throughout the project, as new opportunities arise.

In addition to these specific measures, ObsSea4Clim will strive to create a sense of community and collaboration around the project's ESRs. This will also involve encouraging other formats and opportunities for ESRs to present their work in a relaxed setting, such as during the project's annual meetings, for instance with poster sessions as icebreaker events.

2.1 ObsSea4Clim webinar series

A preliminary list of agreed webinars is presented below. The timeline for the webinar series will be agreed on together with partners responsible for each webinar at a later date. This table will be updated with the date, link to the webinar and recording as this information is confirmed. More information about the practical details of the organisation and sharing of the webinars is included in Section 3.

Table 3 ObsSea4Clim webinar series

Nr.	Topic of the ObsSea4Clim webinar	Contents and Format	Related WP / Task
1	Introduction to data management for ocean observing	<p><u>Contents:</u> data management in the context of ocean observing, examples from other large EU-funded projects.</p> <p><u>Responsible partner:</u> ETT (Beatrice Scotto)</p> <p><u>Format:</u> A 30-40 min webinar with a presentation from ETT, followed by a discussion with other ESRs about key aspects and priorities of data management.</p> <p><u>Audience:</u> ESRs working in oceanography, ocean observing, climate prediction, ESM climate modelling, data management, and the wider climate science scientific community.</p>	WP1 / Task 1.3
2	What is the Rolling Review of Requirements (RRR)?	<p><u>Contents:</u> Where do requirements come from and do you believe they are real? Introduction to the rolling review or requirements (RRR) and its application to ocean EO/ECVs. Impact and evolution of the process.</p> <p><u>Partner:</u> ENS (Sabrina Speich), GEOMAR (Johannes Karstensen)</p> <p><u>Format:</u> A 40 min. webinar with a presentation followed by a Q&A session or small workshop involving ESRs, promoting discussions and generating ideas.</p> <p><u>Audience:</u> ESRs working in oceanography, climate prediction, ESM climate modelling, and the wider climate science scientific community.</p>	WP2 / Task 2.1
3	Best practices and standards for observations - general topic	<p><u>Contents:</u> A general introduction to best practices and standards for observations, challenges and processes proposed by ObsSea4Clim</p>	WP2 / Task 2.2

		<p><u>Partner:</u> IEEE (Jay Pearlman) / possible collaboration with ECOP Ambassadors</p> <p><u>Format:</u> A webinar 30-40 min presentation followed by Q&A.</p> <p><u>Audience:</u> ESRs working in oceanography, climate prediction, ESM climate modelling, and the wider climate science scientific community.</p>	
4	Best practices and standards for observation - focused topic	<p><u>Contents:</u> Focused webinar: presentation of best practices for EOv and concrete use cases. Use cases of WP4 may be used, but these will be added when the results of WP4 are available.</p> <p><u>Partner:</u> IEEE (Jay Pearlman) / possible collaboration with ECOP Ambassador</p> <p><u>Format:</u> A webinar with a 30-40 min presentation followed by a Q&A</p> <p><u>Audience:</u> ESRs working in oceanography, and climate modelling. We will be aiming to attract more focused audiences for whom the concrete use cases/best practices are most relevant, and to encourage focused discussions.</p>	WP 2 / Task 2.2
5	The use of AI algorithms in quantifying uncertainties: foundations and expected advances.	<p><u>Contents:</u> AI is expanding in all areas. What is the potential contribution to uncertainty quantification and quality assurance of EOvs/ECVs?</p> <p><u>Partner:</u> HCMR (Athanasia Papapostolou) in collaboration with ETT</p> <p><u>Format:</u> .A webinar with a 30-40 min presentation followed by a Q&A</p> <p><u>Audience:</u> ESRs working in the field of oceanography, climate prediction, ESM climate modelling</p>	WP 2 / Task 2.3

6	Regionalisation for ocean climate indicators	<p><u>Contents:</u> Why do we need regionalization for indicators? How to test multi-product skills, uncertainties and method sensitivity to enable regionalization of ocean indicators.</p> <p><u>Partner:</u> NUIM (Samantha Hallam)</p> <p><u>Format:</u> A webinar with a 30-40 min presentation followed by a Q&A</p> <p><u>Audience:</u> ESRs working in oceanography, climate prediction, ESM climate modelling, and the wider climate science scientific community.</p>	WP3 / Task 3.1
7	Marine extremes in Europe and in the Arctic area	<p><u>Contents:</u> Development of “driver” and “precursor” indicators for monitoring extreme ocean events.</p> <p><u>Partner:</u> CMCC and NERSC (Ronan McAdam)</p> <p><u>Format:</u> A webinar with a 30-40 minutes presentation followed by a Q&A</p> <p><u>Audience:</u> ESRs working in oceanography, climate prediction, ESM climate modelling, and the wider climate science scientific community.</p>	WP3 / Task 3.2
8	An integrative Approach to ocean indicators	<p><u>Contents:</u> Strategies for an integrated approach for ocean indicators: Introduction to environmental stressors associated with climate impact drivers.</p> <p><u>Partner:</u> MOI (Karina von Schuckmann) and ENS (Sabrina Speich).</p> <p><u>Format:</u> A webinar with a 30-40 minutes presentation followed by a Q&A</p> <p><u>Audience:</u> ESRs working in oceanography, climate prediction, ESM climate modelling, and the wider climate science scientific community.</p>	WP3 / Task 3.3
9	Sea-ice loss: An application area for climate EOVS/ECVs	<p><u>Content:</u> presentations on the application areas of the ObsSea4Clim project.</p> <p><u>Partner:</u> DMI (Pia Englyst)</p> <p><u>Format:</u> A webinar with a 30-40 minutes presentation followed by a Q&A</p> <p>Indicative timeline: after M12</p>	WP 4 / Task 4.1

		<p><u>Audience:</u> ESRs working in oceanography, climate prediction, ESM climate modelling, and the wider climate science scientific community.</p>	
10	Ocean Transport: An application area for climate EO/ECVs	<p><u>Content:</u> An introduction to this specific application area of the ObsSea4Clim project, plan and expected results <u>Partner:</u> Havstovan (Karin M. Larsen and Guðrið Johansen) <u>Format:</u> A webinar of 30-40min covering the specific application areas of WP4, including a Q&A <u>Audience:</u> ESRs working in oceanography, climate prediction, ESM climate modelling, and the wider climate science scientific community</p>	WP4 / Task 4.2
11	Ocean Stratification: An application area for climate EO/ECVs	<p><u>Content:</u> An introduction to this specific application area of the ObsSea4Clim project, plan and expected results. <u>Partner:</u> GEOMAR (Johannes Karstensen) <u>Format:</u> A webinar of 30-40 minutes covering the specific application areas of WP4, including a Q&A <u>Audience:</u> ESRs working in oceanography, climate prediction, ESM climate modelling, and the wider climate science scientific community</p>	WP 4 / Task 4.3
12	Sea level: An application area for climate EO/ECVs	<p><u>Content:</u> An introduction to this specific application area of the ObsSea4Clim project, plan and expected results. <u>Partner:</u> NERSC (Roshin Raj) <u>Format:</u> A webinar with a 30-40 minutes presentation followed by a Q&A. <u>Audience:</u> ESRs working in oceanography, climate prediction, ESM climate modelling, and the wider climate science scientific community</p>	WP 4 / Task 4.4

13	Marine heat waves: An application area for climate EOVs/ECVs	<p><u>Content:</u> An introduction to this specific application area of the ObsSea4Clim project, plan and expected results.</p> <p><u>Partner:</u> CMCC (Ronan McAdam)</p> <p><u>Format:</u> A webinar of 30-40 minutes covering the specific application areas of WP4, including a Q&A</p> <p><u>Audience:</u> ESRs working in oceanography, climate prediction, ESM climate modelling, and the wider climate science scientific community</p>	WP4 / Task 4.5
14	Ocean mesoscale: An application area for climate EOVs/ECVs	<p><u>Content:</u> An introduction to this specific application area of the ObsSea4Clim project, plan and expected results.</p> <p><u>Partner:</u> CSIC (Vincent Combes)</p> <p><u>Format:</u> A webinar with a 30-40 minutes presentation followed by a Q&A</p> <p><u>Audience:</u> ESRs working in oceanography, climate prediction, ESM climate modelling, and the wider climate science scientific community</p>	WP4 / Task 4.6
15	Global and regional ESM evaluation and improvement using EOVs and ECVs	<p><u>Content:</u> How well do ESMs reproduce the phenomena targeted in application areas (sea-ice loss, ocean transport, ocean stratification, sea level, marine heat waves, ocean mesoscale) and how can EOVs and ECVs be used within these models, or to further develop and tune the existing ones.</p> <p><u>Partner:</u> CMCC (Simona Masina)</p> <p><u>Format:</u> AA webinar with a 30-40 minutes presentation followed by a Q&A</p> <p>Indicative timeline: after month 30.</p> <p><u>Audience:</u> ESRs working in oceanography, climate prediction, ESM climate modelling, and the wider climate science scientific community</p>	WP5
16	How to make ObsSea4Clim science actionable: what are	<p><u>Contents:</u> How can ESRs best engage in making science actionable, promoting uptake and understanding of results – co-creation of</p>	WP6

	the best ways to foster uptake?	ideas across partners or disciplines to encourage ESRs? What forms of science dissemination and engagement can be used by ESRs? <u>Partner:</u> EuroGOOS and DMI (Chiara Bearzotti) <u>Format:</u> A webinar, with a participatory discussion. <u>Audience:</u> ESRs working in oceanography, climate prediction, ESM climate modelling, and the wider climate science scientific community, participatory research...	
17	How to make ObsSea4Clim science actionable: which are the best ways to communicate science?	<u>Contents:</u> How can ESRs best engage and communicate in making science actionable, promoting uptake and understanding of results – co-creation of ideas across partners or disciplines to encourage ESRs? What forms of science dissemination and engagement can be used by ESRs? <u>Partner:</u> +ATLANTIC (Tiago Garcia) and potential collaboration with BioEcoOcean partner <u>Format:</u> A webinar with 2 presentations, with a participatory discussion. <u>Audience:</u> ESRs working in oceanography, climate prediction, ESM climate modelling, and the wider climate science scientific community <u>In collaboration with</u> BioEcoOcean (sister project) and the Networking Fridays initiative (MBON/ AirCenter)	WP6

2.2 Participation of ObsSea4Clim ESRs in other existing webinar series

ObsSea4Clim will also encourage ESRs working on the project to participate in other ongoing initiatives to present their work. These activities aim to provide a setting for ESRs to practice presenting to a wide audience, to discuss their research with the

community in a relaxed setting and to connect with other researchers. The following opportunities have been identified. This list will be revised and expanded throughout the project if other opportunities arise.

Table 4 Collaboration with other existing webinar series

Name of initiative	Description of content and format	WP
<p>Climate Coffees for early-stage researchers</p> <p><i>Climate Coffees are organized by the Project Office, with the support of the European Climate Research Alliance and in collaboration with the Horizon project OCEAN:ICE, Horizon Europe project TipESM. The activities will be broadened to ObsSea4Clim</i></p>	<p><u>Contents:</u> ESRs involved in the project to present their work on climate-related results (<i>from social sciences to physical oceanography every topic is interesting!</i>).</p> <p><u>Leading partner:</u> DMI</p> <p><u>Format:</u> A webinar with a 30-minute presentation and a 10-minute Q&A</p> <p><u>Audience:</u> Researchers from the wider climate science scientific community</p>	<p>Across WPs</p>
<p>Promotion and invitation to webinar series at partner institutions</p>	<p><u>Contents:</u> Climate modelling and ocean science</p> <p><u>Partner:</u> Partners in the consortium</p> <p><u>Format:</u> To follow the existing format at each institute.</p> <p>Project partner institutions (e.g. CMCC) to be in charge of webinar organisation, speaker selection and administrative aspects. For relevant webinars where ObsSea4Clim researchers may be invited as audience or speakers, the Project Office will support distributing information about the webinar to relevant audiences</p>	<p>Across WPs</p>

	<p><u>Audience:</u> ObsSea4Clim ESRs, other researchers and researchers from the wider oceanography and climate science scientific community</p>	
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2.3 Synergies with existing ESR networks

ObsSea4Clim will aim to collaborate with existing ESR networks to create joint activities for the benefit of ESR. The following networks have been identified due to their relevance and existing links between them and project partners:

- [ECOP – Early Career Ocean Professionals](#)
- [APECS – Association of Polar Early Career Scientists](#)

The Project Office will explore possible synergies such as

- Promotion of the ObsSea4Clim webinar series among these networks
- Encourage ObsSea4Clim ESRs to participate in ECOP/APECS webinars, events or workshops
- Mutual dissemination and communication of activities through social media channels or websites.

2.4 ESR participation in fieldwork

While fieldwork activities are not planned nor funded under the ObsSea4Clim project directly, some of the partners in the consortium (GEOMAR for instance) often offer possibilities to ESR to join fieldwork activities as a learning opportunity. Therefore, the ObsSea4Clim Project Office will collaborate with partners offering these options to promote these actions to the ESR working in ObsSea4Clim by:

- Promoting upcoming open opportunities in which ESRs may be able to participate
- Sharing of materials (such as blog posts, short articles, and social media posts) through the social media channels and website of ObsSea4cClim
- Providing ESRs who have participated in fieldwork with the opportunity to present their work at an ObsSea4Clim webinar or meeting

The list of the opportunities will be shared with the ObsSea4Clim partners and will be published on the website.

3 Practical details

3.1 Promotion of the capacity building measures

Capacity-building measures will be promoted on the project website, social channels and the network built with other projects and initiatives.

The ObsSea4Clim webinar series (Section 2.1) will be recorded and the recordings will be made available on the ObsSea4Clim channel on YouTube. The presentation slides for each webinar will be made available in Zenodo, in open access. The Question and Answer (Q&A) sessions will not be recorded.

3.2 Organisation of the Capacity Building Measures

The webinar series listed above (Section 2.1) will be organised by the Project Office: the Project Office will handle the registration of the participants, the set up of the webinars, the moderation and the follow-up of the webinars.

Priority in the registration to webinars will be given to ESR affiliated with the project and its consortium partners.

All participants will sign an informed consent form. The management and collection of data will be implemented in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Liaison with other networks and initiatives (Section 2.2, Section 2.3) will also be handled by the Project Office, particularly for the organisation or logistics of possible joint activities and joint communication or dissemination of event plans.

3.3 Follow-up of the Capacity Building Measures

An evaluation questionnaire will be sent to all participants to ask for feedback on the training.

3.4 Update of the plan

This plan will be updated by May 2026 (MS11), with an update covering the period from June 2026 to the end of the project.

